

Trade Openness and Economic Growth in the Central African Republic (CAR): Application of the VECM

Karl-Lesin BEBONA^{1*}

¹Capital University of Economic and Business (CUEB), China

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*Corresponding Author:
Karl-Lesin BEBONA,
karl_lezin@yahoo.fr

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to empirically analyze the relationship between trade openness and economic growth in Central African Republic for the period 1980-2020. To do this, the study applied time series techniques such as Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test to check the stationarity of variables, the Johansen cointegration test for the long run relationship, the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) for short run dynamics and to estimate the speed of adjustment towards long run equilibrium. We also carried out tests on the residuals to see the econometric robustness of the model. The study shows that GDP growth responds faster at a speed of 30.79% than all others variable (OPEN, LABOR and GFCF). The results of the cointegration equation show that an increase of unit of trade openness leads to a decrease of 0.67 units of GDP. The main findings suggest there is negative long run relationship between trade openness and economic growth in the Central African Republic (CAR).

Keywords: TRADE OPENNESS ,ECONOMIC GROWTH ,CENTRAL AFRICAN REPUBLIC, VECTOR ERROR CORRECTION MODEL

1. Introduction

The development of theories economic growth has highlighted the central role of trade openness as a factor that can promote growth. Several economic studies confirm the existence of a causal link between trade

openness and economic growth (Michaley, 1977; Frankel and Romer, 1999). Thus, several studies show that with adequate opening policies and a minimum level of development, trade openness has technological spillovers, contributes to human capital formation, facilitates integration into international trade, promotes the creation of a more competitive business climate and improves business development. All these factors contribute to the acceleration of economic growth, which is the most powerful instrument for fighting poverty in developing countries. The results of these different studies clearly confirm the existence of a significant positive relationship between openness and growth (Wacziarg R., and Welch, H.K., 2008).

In the current context of globalization, it is natural to question the links between trade openness and economic

growth. If a positive and significant impact of openness on growth can be unambiguously established, it will encourage developing countries wishing to improve their economic situation to adopt trade liberalization policies. Moreover, the economic emergence of East Asian countries confirms the idea that trade openness is a factor of growth.

For this purpose, a number of international organizations encourage countries to liberalize their borders and trade with the rest of the world. For some international institutions such as the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank, trade openness is a major condition for granting financial aid or economic assistance to developing countries.

This condition raises the reality of Sub-Saharan African countries, including the Central African Republic, which in the 1980s adhered to the policy of economic openness, characterized by the total liberalization of its economy under the GATT agreements and the structural adjustment program.

Thus, during the past decade we have witnessed the implementation of policies affecting areas as diverse as the economy, education, health, administration whose main objectives were to clean up the macroeconomic framework, promote economic growth, improve the performance of real sectors of the economy, promote the development of human capital and good governance etc.

Adjustment in CAR dates back to the first structural adjustment program (SAP) in 1986. Since then, the country has been under adjustment with the implementation of several programs, including the economic policy framework document agreed with the IMF in 1998.

Despite its political commitment and geostrategic position in Central Africa, the country does not benefit enough from its trade openness. CAR's trade with the rest of the world is weak. The inadequacy and above all the mediocrity of the transport infrastructure and the deterioration of the business climate, which essentially explain this poor performance, are all obstacles to the structural transformation of the economy.

The objective of this study is to answer the following question: Does trade openness positively affect economic growth in the Central African Republic?

To do this, we organized our work as follows: the first section concerns the introduction of our study, the second section will present a review of the literature on the relationship between trade openness and economic growth; the third section will present the data sources; the fourth section will focus on the econometric method and the empirical results obtained; and the fifth section will present the conclusion of our work.

2. Review of theoretical and empirical literature

2.1. Theoretical review

Based on the idea of pure and perfect competition and constant returns to scale, the traditional theory of international trade advocates for the trade openness and argues for free trade, because this allows domestic

production to rise.

Indeed, by directing its resources towards the sector of activity where it has an absolute advantage, comparative or which intensively use the factor with which it is abundantly endowed, an open country achieves production gains favorable to its economic growth.

David Ricardo, in the 19th century, through his theory of comparative advantage, demonstrated that the more open a country is, the more it allows it to redirect its scarce resources to more efficient sectors and improve its welfare. Several theoretical studies have confirmed these gains, in addition to adding those related to the remuneration of production factors.

(Solow, 1957) argues that technological change is exogenous. In such a framework, a country's trade policies cannot therefore be considered as an element affecting its growth. The exogenous growth model, proposed by Solow & Swan, based its explanation of economic growth on the savings rate (constant) in the short run, and on technological progress (exogenous) in the long run. In the short run, the economy is supposed to be in a transition phase. During this transition phase, openness policies can play an accelerating role in income convergence, in particular by acting on the capital stock.

This model also distinguishes two types of trajectories (convergence): absolute convergence for countries with the same characteristics and conditional convergence for countries with different regular states.

For endogenous growth theorists (Romer, 1994), long run economic growth is a cumulative dynamic of physical capital, population growth, technical progress, the process of internal learning and economic behavior and the level of human capital.

Thus, the economic opening will allow the increase of this factor and even the quantity of available knowledge, automatically leading to an acceleration of growth. In this analytical framework, countries always have an interest in opening up, since openness facilitates the process of convergence towards the level of development of developed countries.

(Grossman and Helpman, 1991 and Levin and Raut (1997) show that economic openness leads to increased competition, which forces countries to make the structural changes necessary to maintain competitiveness, which then requires a certain level of human capital capable of dealing with technological change.

However, openness can lead to the closure of firms that are driving growth. In this context, a temporary protectionist trade policy would allow countries to accumulate the know-how necessary for their competitiveness (Krugman, 1987).

(Coe and Helpman, 1995) are interested in the role of trade openness in the international transmission of technology from advanced to developing countries. As the research and development effort of developing

countries remains low, it is through the import of capital goods and FDI that these countries can benefit from global technology.

On the other hand (Benhabib and Spiegel, 1994), show that the application of these technologies requires the presence of a sufficient level of human capital to support them. The interaction between human capital and economic openness is also found in the model of (Berthelmy and Varoudakis 1997).

The benefits of trade openness depend on country-specific conditions. Indeed, if certain conditions are met, such as qualified human capital, openness stimulates growth insofar as it strengthens the country's reaction to external shocks. (Fontagné and Guénin, 1997) indicate that the internal conditions of a country determine the effect of openness on its growth.

(Edwards, 1998) uses comparative data from 93 countries to analyze the robustness of the relationship between openness and total factor productivity growth. The results show that openness countries experienced faster productivity growth.

2.2. Empirical review

The empirical literature that examines the relationship between trade openness and growth does not provide very clear answers, because this relationship is quite complex. There does not seem to be a single conclusion regarding the relationship between trade openness and economic growth. It is clear that the results seem to be sensitive to the choice of variables, countries, time periods, and econometric techniques used and also to the statistical data available. Almost all empirical studies between the late 1970s and the late 1990s confirm the existence of positive link between trade openness and economic growth.

The emerging results of the study by (Sachs and Warner 1995) classified countries into two groups, open and closed, based on an assessment of their trade policies as well as a set of other criteria. The results showed that it is only in open economies that unconditional convergence can be observed.

(Harrison, 1996) uses seven indicators often encountered in the literature, performing OLS estimates, finds a positive relationship between these indicators and economic growth. Using the instrumental variables method including geographic characteristics, (Frankel and Romer, 1998) show that international trade has a large and significant impact on growth.

(Combes and al, 2000) have shown that openness is not the only determinant of growth. Openness is only a necessary but not sufficient condition for the catching-up process. These authors concluded that trade openness requires economic reforms and better ability to manage external shocks, which reduces the instability of economic growth.

(Caupin and Saad-Sedik, 2003) analyze the effects of trade openness policy on the instability of growth rates

using a regression model and conclude that openness policy has a beneficial effect on the resilience of countries.

(Kum & Lin 2009) analyze the relationship between trade and growth at different stages of economic development; the results suggest that there is an income threshold above which trade openness has beneficial effects on economic growth

Using the Granger causality test and the VAR model on 28 countries over the period 1962-1997, (Lewer 2010) found that for countries that imported consumer goods and exported capital goods, it was difficult for them to experience economic growth over the medium term, while countries that imported capital goods and exported consumer goods experienced a decline in costs to replace depreciated capital.

(Adhikary, 2011) analyzes the relationship between FDI, trade openness, capital formation, and economic growth rates in Bangladesh over a period from 1986 to 2008 using time series analysis, the results suggest that trade openness influences negatively economic growth.

(Dekkiche djamale, 2012) studied of the influence of trade openness on economic growth in Algeria, during the period 1992-2009. The econometric study was based on several tests and used autoregressive distributed lag (ADRL) models, the results show that there is positive and significant relationship between trade openness and economic growth in Algeria.

(Gries and Redlin, 2012) studied the short and long-run dynamics between GDP per capita growth and the degree of openness for 158 countries. Using panel cointegration tests and error correction models, the results show that there is positive relationship between trade openness and economic growth in long run. In contrast, the short-run coefficients reveal a negative effect.

Analyzing the relationship between financial development, trade openness and economic growth for 21 Sub-Saharan countries, (Menyah, Nazlioglu and Wolde-Rufaelet 2014) show limited support for the hypothesis of trade-led growth for the Sub-Saharan African countries studied.

Results of (Ulaşan 2015) on dynamic panel data suggest that trade openness alone does not stimulate economic growth.

Studies by (Trejos & Barboza 2015) on the relationship between trade openness and output growth show that trade openness can promote per capita output growth through productivity gain associated with capital accumulation, rather than through assumed technological spillovers.

(Kamel and Dib, 2016) analyze the nature of the link between international trade and economic growths in Algeria, using tests and VECM during the period 1970-2013, find that international trade plays a negative role in driving economic growth in Algeria.

(Zahonogo P. 2016), by testing the effect of trade liberalization on growth through cross-sectional regression of 42 sub-Saharan African countries covering the period 1980 to 2012, the results suggest that the effects of trade openness on economic growth depend on its trade threshold.

(Iyoha and Okim 2017) econometrically test the hypothesis of positive relationship between trade and growth in ECOWAS countries over the period 1990-2013 using panel data regression analysis. The results show that exports, exchange rate, and investment are important determinants of real per capita income growth. Exports have positive effects on growth, confirming the hypothesis that trade has positive and significant impact on economic growth in ECOWAS countries.

(Teignier, 2018) analyzed the role of international agricultural trade in structural transformation for South Korea in the last 50 years and Britain in the 19th century. The results suggest that agricultural imports play a large role in Britain than in South Korea.

Using the Panel Correction Standard Error (PCSE) technique to analyze the relationship between trade, investment and growth in Sub-Saharan African countries, (Ikpesu, Olusegun and Dakare, 2019) find that trade, domestic investment, and imports are positively affecting growth in the region, while exportations are negatively affecting growth.

(Bekihal and Adouka, 2020) present an empirical study evaluating the impact of trade openness on economic development in Algeria during the period 2000-2015. The results show a mixed effect of the trade openness process on economic growth in Algeria.

(Karim and Attoumane, 2021) study the long run and short run dynamics between trade openness and economic growth over the period 1999 to 2019 for 35 African countries. The results show that there is a cointegration relationship between the variables and that the effects of trade openness on growth depend on the level of trade openness.

3. Materials and methods

This study uses secondary data. All data are collected from the World Bank database (World Development Indicators). Based on the theoretical and empirical work developed on trade openness and economic growth as well as on the economic policy implemented by the Central African government, we have taken into account the following variables.

Gross domestic product (GDP) is the sum of gross value added by all resident producers in the economy plus any product taxes and minus any subsidies not included in the value of the population. Data are in current U.S. dollars.

Trade openness (OPEN) can indeed have two effects on growth, a direct effect through increased capacity

utilization and production efficiency, and indirect effect through increased exports. The trade openness is equal to the sum of imports and exports on gross domestic product (GDP).

Labor force (LABOR) is defined as all people of working age who are available on the labor market, whether they have a job or whether they are unemployed, unlike those not seeking no employment, such as homemakers, students, people unable to work, pensioners. The amount of work done in an economy is proportional to its labor force. The latter is supposed to have a positive impact on economic growth (GDP), with a threshold effect according to the economic theory of diminishing marginal returns.

Gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) as a proxy for the physical capital has been used in several studies. Physical capital is all the capital owned by businesses in a country that is used by them to produce goods or services. Investment in physical capital, above all, in infrastructure reduces transaction costs, which is likely to promote economic growth (GDP).

For a correct assessment of the impact of trade opening on economic growth in the Central African Republic, the choice of VECM (Vector Error Correction Model) is justified by the fact that it makes it possible to model the adjustments that lead to long-run equilibrium situation. It is a model that integrates both short and long run equilibrium relationship. If the variables are cointegrated this means there is a long run relationship between the variables. Thus, we can use the VECM (Vector Error Correction Model) to evaluate the short run dynamics. Furthermore, if there is not cointegration relationship between the variables, the VECM cannot be used. We can directly apply Granger causality test to analyze relationship between the variables.

To analyze the long run equilibrium relationship between the variables, ADF test (1981) and Johansen cointegration test (1988) are used. Thus, the regression equation for VECM can be written as follows:

$$\Delta Y_t = a_1 + a_1 e_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta_i \Delta X_{t-i} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta X_t = a_1 + a_1 e_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^n \beta_i \Delta X_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \delta_1 \Delta Y_{t-i} \quad (2)$$

In Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), the cointegration rank indicates the number of cointegration vectors. If for example the rank is one, this means that there is a single cointegration vector. The Error Correction Component (ECM) given as the coefficient of e_{t-1} suggests the speed of adjustment of the variables towards long run equilibrium after short run fluctuations of the variables.

Thus, we specify the model with an endogenous variable (GDP) and the multi-varied exogenous variables namely, OPEN, LABOR, GFCF. The basic equation for estimating the impact of trade openness on economic growth is as follows:

$$GDP = f(OPEN, LABOR, GFCF) \quad (3)$$

For the application of multivariate econometric techniques, the above stated model can be expressed in the

following linear logarithmic form:

$$\ln GDP_t = a_0 + a_1 \ln OPEN_t + a_2 \ln LABOR_t + a_3 \ln GFCF_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

To do this, we will successively perform a certain number of statistical tests while making the necessary corrections in order to estimate the coefficients of the selected model. Post-estimation tests will also be carried out on this model in order to certify its validity.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Graphical analysis

Graph 1: Evolution of the study variables

Source: Based on Stata 14 Software results

The graphs of four variables gross domestic product (GDP), trade openness (OPEN), labor force (LABOR) and gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) above, show the presence of trend for each variable. Thus, we go to check the stationarity of the series.

4.2. Testing for Stationarity

The analysis of ADF (Dickey-Fuller Augmented) test allows us to determine the order of integration, if the variable is stationary in level, this means that its order of integration is zero; and if the variable admits stationarity in first difference, this means the order of integration can go from 1 to n.

Table 1: Results ADF Unit Root Test

Test results at the 5% threshold				
Variables	Dickey-Fuller Augmented (ADF)			Stationarity
	t-statistic	Critical value	Probability	Order of integration
GDP	-4.095	-3.548	0.0064	I(1)
OPEN	-5.407	-3.548	0.0000	I(1)
LABOR	-3.573	-3.548	0.0322	I(1)
GFCF	-5.076	-3.548	0.0001	I(1)

Source: Based on Stata14 Software results

The table1 shows that all variables are stationary in first difference at the 5% threshold. So this means that all variables are integrated to order one.

4.3. Selection of Optimal Lag Length

Determining the optimal lag length is necessary to perform the VECM. To do this, two information criteria are used [AKAIKE (AIC), Schwarz (SC)]. We chose the lag length of the VAR in levels that minimizes the information criteria.

Table 2: Results of Lag Length selection

lag	LL	LR	FPE	AIC	HQIC	SBIC
0	141.734		8.4 ^e -0.9	-7.24918	-7.18785	-7.0768
1	222.203	160.94*	2.8^e-10*	-10.6423*	-10.3356*	-9.7804*
2	234.378	23.614	3.6 ^e -10	-10.4216	-9.86963	-8.8702
3	242.378	16.735	5.9 ^e -10	-10.0199	-9.22259	-7.77898

Source: Based on Stata 14 software results

The results give us an optimal VAR of order one, this means we will estimate an autoregressive model of order one.

4.4. Testing for cointegration

After confirmation that the time series are stationary and integrated to the same order (the same level), it can be concluded that there is a single cointegration vector. To confirm this conclusion, the JOHANSEN cointegration test is used.

Table 3: Results of Johansen co-integration test

Maximum rank	parms	LL	eigenvalue	Trace statistic	Critical value 5%
0	4	206.34522	-	52.1858	47/21
1	11	219.83346	0.49054	25.2093*	29,68
2	16	226.18763	0.27218	12.5009	15.41
3	19	230.92734	0.21100	3.0215	3.76
4	20	232.4331	0.07276	-	-

Source: Based on Stata14 Software results

The table3 shows that there is long run equilibrium relationship between the variables namely GDP, OPEN, LABOR and GFCF. This results suggests also that the variables are cointegrated with cointegration rank of order one (1). These findings indicate that the appropriate model to fit in the data is VECM.

4.5. Estimation of the VECM for GDP

The results of Johansen cointegration test suggest that VECM is appropriate for modeling the relationship between GDP growth and OPEN, LABOR, and GFCF. Further, the VECM also reports the short run relationship amongst variables and how they adjust towards long run equilibrium. From Table4, the cointegration equation between GDP growth and OPEN, LABOR, and GFCF for Central African Republic in the period of 1980-2020 is given as:

$$\ln GDP = -73.70 - .673 \ln OPEN + 20.01 \ln LABOR + 1.12 \ln GFCF \quad (5)$$

Table4: Co-integration equation Johansen normalization restriction imposed

Bera	Coef	Std. Error	z	P> z
_ce1				
<i>lnGDP</i>	1	-	-	-
<i>lnOPEN</i>	.6735195	.2893068	2.33	0.020
<i>lnLABOR</i>	-20.0106	7.965366	-2.51	0.012
<i>lnGFCF</i>	-1.123268	.1988738	-5.65	0.000
_cons	73.70186	-	-	-

Source: Based on Stata 14 Software results

Through empirical verification, the VECM shows that in the long run, trade openness negatively affects economic growth in the CAR, while it positively affects its evolution in the short run. The result of the cointegrating equation shows that an increase of one unit of trade openness leads to a decrease of 0.67 units of GDP. So we can conclude that trade openness has a negative impact on the economic growth in the Central African economy.

Regarding labor force and gross fixed capital formation, we find that the latter have positive effects on GDP, since an increase of one unit of labor force and gross fixed capital formation generates respectively an increase of 20.01 units and 1.12 units of GDP. The Table4 shows also that the coefficients of all variables are significant.

The table5 below shows the results for the individual adjustment of the variables in the short run towards the long run equilibrium.

Table5: Adjustment parameters

alpha	Coef	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]
D_ lnGDP					
_ce1	-.3078663	.0847159	-3.63	0.000	-.4739069 -.1418266
L1.					
D_ lnOPEN					
_ce1	.1003638	.0648979	1.55	0.122	-.0268339 .2275614
L1.					
D_ lnLABOR					
_ce1	-.0052014	.0038711	-1.34	0.179	-.0127887 .0023859
L1.					
D_ lnGFCF					
_ce1	.1817881	.1656864	1.10	0.273	-.1429513 .5065275
L1.					

Source: Based on Stata 14 Software results

The results shows that, GDP growth responds faster (at a speed of 30.79%) than all others variable (OPEN, LABOR and GFCF) towards long run equilibrium if there is a disequilibrium in the economy in the short run. This is expected since GDP growth depends on other factors for it to increase hence should respond faster than variables which are independent from other factors such as OPEN. For the other variables, GFCF responds faster (18.18%) than OPEN (10.04%) and LABOR (0.52%)

4.6. Tests on the residuals

Before concluding the results economically, we must test the econometric robustness of the model, which is assessed by the Jarque and Béra normality test administered to each equation, serial independence test of the Lagrange multiplier and error autocorrelation test.

4.6.1. Normality test

Table6: Jarque-Bera test

Equation	Chi2	df	Prob >chi2
D_InGDP	6.378	2	0.04120
D_InOPEN	0.851	2	0.65356
D_InLABOR	5.961	2	0.05078
D_InGFCF	0.179	2	0.91418
ALL	13.369	8	0.09976

Source: Based on Stata 14 Software results

The results obtained from this test show that the probability (P-value) is equal to 0.09976, (a probability that is greater than 5%). Thus we can suggest that the variables of our model follow the normal distribution. The tests carried out show that the model is stationary and stable and thus a normal distribution of variables. So we can say econometrically that our model is a valid model.

4.6.2. Stability test

Table7: Eigen value stability condition

Eigenvalue	Modulus
1	1
1	1
1	1
.3682916+.2110427i	.424474
.3682916 - .2110427i	.424474
-.3830253	.383025
-.1164128 - .1143464i	.163178
-.1164123 -.1143464i	.163178

The VECM specification imposes 3 unit moduli.

Source: Based on Stata 14 Software results

4.6.3. Error autocorrelation test

Table 8: Lagrange-multiplier test

lag	Chi2	df	Prob>chi2
1	10.4179	16	0.84391
2	6.4544	16	0.98240

Source: Based on Stata 14 Software results

The various econometric tests carried out show that our model is well specified, that there is no autocorrelation of errors and that the model is structurally and cyclically stable. So we can conclude that the econometric robustness of the model is satisfactory.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we use the stationarity test, the Johansen cointegration test and the VECM, and the residual error tests to analyze the relationship between trade openness and economic growth in the Central African Republic over period 1980-2020. The results suggest all variables, such as GDP, OPEN, LABOR and GFCF, are stationary in first difference and cointegrated; they evolve together and display a long run relationship.

The cointegration equation shows that trade openness has a negative and significant impact on the economic growth in the Central African Republic in the long run. However labor force and gross fixed capital formation have positive and significant effects on GDP. Furthermore, the results show that short run fluctuations are adjusted towards long run equilibrium at a speed of approximately 30.79%. Thus, the various econometric tests we have carried out have shown that our model is globally significant, that there is no autocorrelation of errors that the distribution is normal and therefore consequently the model is structurally and cyclically stable.

This study notes that the CAR's trade balance is structurally in deficit and that this deficit is most marked in trade in goods. The products exported are essentially primary and not very diversified. Imports are fairly diversified, but remain mainly oriented towards basic necessities. By taking measures to stimulate domestic production, the Central African government could actively contribute to reducing the trade deficit. In addition, through tax relief on capital goods imports, the CAR can promote the transfer of technology necessary for industrial development.

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